

Determination of polarimetric capabilities of the Thirty Meter Telescope

Ramya M Anche

Steward Observatory, University of Arizona, 933 North Cherry Avenue, Tucson, AZ 85721-0065, USA

Polarimetry is an important observational technique in astronomy in addition to photometry and spectroscopy. Polarization arises as a consequence of asymmetry; such as the presence of magnetic fields, interstellar dust, distribution of scattered radiation, etc. Polarization observations enable us to understand the nature and composition of dust, strength of magnetic fields, asymmetry in the structure of the source [1]. Currently, imaging/Spectropolarimeter has been an important instrument at many 1-10m class telescopes[2]. The polarimetric capability will be a crucial add-on to the imaging/spectroscopic instruments for the next-generation Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs).

One potential problem for accurate polarimetry is the polarization introduced/modified by the telescope and instrument optics due to non-normal incidences on the optical surface. Non-zero polarization measured at the telescope focus for the unpolarized light, incident on the telescope, is Instrumental polarization (IP). The loss of input polarization is called depolarization (DP), and the conversion of linear to circular polarization (or vice versa) is crosstalk (CT) [3]. In addition to IP, CT, and DP, there may be polarization-induced aberrations; ex., coating-induced astigmatism, tilt, defocus, and chromatic aberrations [4, 5]. Polarization aberrations can cause ghost PSF during the high-contrast imaging of planets/disks. So estimation of these aberrations before the instrument design through modeling is crucial to ascertain their effect on the scientific observations.

Polarization is measured using Stokes parameters [6] which describe the polarization of light in terms of intensity measurements (I, Q, U, V). The 4×4 matrix representation which is used to study the interaction of polarized (or unpolarized) light with elements that modify the polarization is **Mueller matrix** given by Mueller [7].

The polarization effects introduced by telescope and instrument optics are usually corrected by polarization modeling and observations of standard polarized and unpolarized stars [8]. Here, We describe an analytical model (based on polarization ray tracing) developed to estimate the polarization effects for one of the next-generation large telescopes, the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT).

Thirty meter Telescope

The Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) is one of the large segmented mirror telescopes, proposed to be located in Mauna Kea, Hawaii, USA. It is a consortium between the USA, Canada, India, China, and Japan. The telescope is expected to have its first light in 2028 [9] The primary mirror is 30 m in diameter and made of 492 hexagonal segments, each measuring 1.44m across. An elliptical-

shaped Nasmyth mirror rotates and tilts to feed light to different instruments on the Nasmyth platform [10]. ^{##}

Polarization ray tracing algorithm for TMT

In our model (Figure 1), we use Gemini coating[11] for all the three mirrors, and estimate instrumental polarization, crosstalk, and depolarization at the Nasmyth focus of TMT for $\lambda=0.4-2.5\mu m$ and field of view of $10'$. IP, CT, and DP are found to increase with the field angle due to the asymmetry and reduce with the wavelength due to the nature of the coating as shown in Figure 2. Nasmyth/fold mirror is the main source for the polarization effects in TMT[12].

Figure 1: Algorithm for polarization ray tracing developed for TMT[13]

Figure 2: The variation of IP for semi field angle of $10'$ with the wavelength range of $0.4 \mu m$ to $2.5 \mu m$

The Mueller matrices are estimated for different in-

^{##}<https://www.tmt.org/>

strument ports on the Nasmyth platform for different zenith angles of the telescope. The IP, CT, and DP are found to vary with the zenith angle of the telescope at all the instrument ports except at the Wide-field Optical Spectrograph (WFOS) port [10, 12].

Crossed mirror configuration for TMT for polarization cancellation

To reduce/cancel the polarization effects introduced by the Nasmyth mirror, another fold mirror can be added in the crossed configuration. This has been implemented successfully in the VLT telescope for SPHERE. Using a similar configuration shown in Figure 3, we have achieved polarization cancellation up to 10^{-3} (0.1%) from 4% and Linear to circular cross talk reduced to 4% from 70% in the blue region[14].

Figure 3: Crossed fold mirror configuration for TMT for polarization cancellation

To increase the accuracy of our estimation of IP, CT, and DP, we included the segments of the primary mirror in our model using optical design software Zemax. We analyzed the following effects with a segmented model: 1. Refractive index of silver and silicon nitride variation from segment to segment 2. Re-coating sequence of segments. 3. Tilt and Piston variation of segments.

Estimation of polarization aberrations

We have used the above ray tracing algorithm to estimate the polarization aberrations in the TMT in terms of Jones pupil maps. These aberrations give rise to the ghost PSF, which leads to ellipticity of the Airy disk. Polarization-induced aberrations in TMT are found to be coating-induced astigmatism ($\lambda/70$), tilt ($\lambda/12$ at $0.6\mu\text{m}$),

and chromatic aberration. The intensity of the ghost PSF generated due to polarization aberrations has also been estimated for the Narrow Field Infrared Adaptive Optics System (NFIRAOS) of TMT in Anche et al. [15].

Summary and Conclusions

We have modeled the polarization effects from the telescope optics of the Thirty Meter Telescope. Instrumental polarization varies from 4-0.6%, crosstalk varies from 70-10%, and depolarization varies from 2.5-0.8% in the wavelength range of $0.4\text{-}2.5\mu\text{m}$ for field angle zero. The polarization effect varies with the field angle and zenith angle of the telescope and, reduces with the wavelength (near/mid-infrared region). A mid-infrared instrument, MICH (Mid- Infrared Camera, High-disperser, and Integral field unit) could be a possible second-generation instrument with the polarimetric capability[16] for TMT.

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Short CV

- 2014: Master in Astronomical Instrumentation, IIA, India
- 2015–2019: PhD in Astronomical Instrumentation, University of Calcutta & IIA, India
- 2019–2020: Research Engineer, NAO, Beijing, China
- 2020–2021: WALOP Postdoctoral fellow, IUCAA, Pune, India
- 2021–present: Postdoctoral Research Associate, University of Arizona, USA